

AN OVERVIEW OF THE SOCIOECONOMIC VULNERABILITY OF FAMILY GROUPS IN BRAZIL

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Abstract

Socioeconomic vulnerability is growing as a result of a process of global concentration of income, which is currently aggravated by the global pandemic. Economies that are already fragile like Latin American countries need a proposal solution to the suppression elementary of vulnerable populations. Through more effective social benefit distribution programs adapted to the new reality can be defines the best characteristics of vulnerability of these populations. In this way, the study presents a scale for assessing levels of socioeconomic vulnerability of family groups already registered with CadÚnico (Database Families), this database being the main reference for the distribution of benefits by the federal government, states and municipalities in Brazil. The methodology used was the IRT (Item Response Theory), whose assumptions suggest a qualitative and quantitative approach based on the response patterns obtained from the beneficiaries of the Bolsa Família Program, adapting them to the items suggested by the methodology itself. The results indicate that the socioeconomic vulnerability levels defined with the created scale make it possible to estimate, proportionally and within a regional perspective, family groups served or not by the same Program between the years 2012 and 2018.

Keywords: Vulnerability; Social Policies ; Unique Cad ; Item Response Theory.

Introduction

Social Policies are understood as those that aim at the well-being of a population , originating from complex state interventions that establish and adjust the processes of social reproduction, operating indirectly on the existing relations between capital and labor (CHAVES; GEHLEN, 2019). For the State, social policies are an arm of public policies, which seek to meet specific demands of their users, through citizen rights and the guarantee of social protection (AUGUSTO, 1989, EHRING; BOSCHETTI, 2009, SILVA; ALMEIDA , 2009).

They also have a distributive character, being mainly intended for the lower income population, in a situation of poverty proven by their socioeconomic profile . Therefore, social policies aim at the economic development of the portion of individuals in a state of social vulnerability and the elimination of poverty, reducing inequalities through income redistribution.

Social vulnerability refers to a circumstance that indicates the fragility of the socioeconomic situation of an individual or group, who are on the margins of society and in the process of social exclusion (CARMO; GUIZARDI, 2018).

According to Moser and Bronkhorst (1999), the concept of vulnerability is an effective tool to analyze the situation of the socially excluded in Latin America, as it is capable of broadly understanding the diversities and behaviors existing in the reality of the poor that go beyond the attributes of income. . This is because the concept of changing socioeconomic well-being in poor communities has multidimensional aspects and requires the identification of levels of poverty and types of vulnerabilities. Moser (1998) differentiates the concepts, often taken as synonyms, of poverty and vulnerability. Poverty measures are, in general, fixed in time, constituting a static concept. Unlike vulnerability which is more dynamic being more sensitive as people move in and out of poverty.

Medeiros (2000) characterizes Latin America by dispersed, fragmented social policies with limited distributive power. It highlights the role of families in contextualizing the application of public policies (*welfare state*) in Latin America and warns about the necessary adaptations to face the needs of Latin American society and the ability of individuals to satisfy them. This is because the differences in living and working conditions are notorious when compared to the populations of North America and Western Europe. Mota (2012) refers to economic growth and poverty reduction in Latin America and Brazil, however it shows that such events are based on intervention mechanisms in emergency situations of poverty without constituting universal rights or instituting them as policies public, but only as government programs.

Abramovay *et al.* (2002), when dealing with analytical approaches related to social vulnerability, state that they only date from the end of the 20th century and bring reflections on the limitations of studies on poverty and the scarce results of policies associated with them in Latin America. They show that such studies, despite serving to identify the most deprived sectors of the population to be served, through social policies, could not explain the complex roots of this phenomenon, because they are based only on the use of indicators of income or needs that delimit the dissatisfaction of basic needs.

Thus, despite the limitations presented by Abramovay *et al.* (2002) on previous studies, all problem analysis involves the evaluation of studies already carried out, of data or statistics that may represent the profiles of supposedly more vulnerable social groups due to their condition of age, gender, minority group, socioeconomic status or other related variables such as the results of assessments carried out by independent agencies or communities affected by the problem situation that is intended to be understood. In Brazil, there are important secondary data sources, and generally the one used as a reference in the design of Federal Government Social Programs is the Single Registry prepared and updated annually by the IBGE (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics).

2. The Single Registry

The Single Registry (CadÚnico) is an instrument that seeks to demonstrate the characteristics of families and individuals in a state of social vulnerability, and its idea is to unify, in the same database, current and potential beneficiaries of social programs. Therefore, it consists of a support for the creation of social policies, considering that it gathers data on the risks and vulnerabilities to which some social groups are particularly exposed (SEDES, 2020).

There are two reference bases available that are part of CadÚnico: one made up of Families and the other made up of Individuals, both determined year by year, depending on the permanence of existing records, new entries and exits. Since 2012, the CadÚnico das Famílias database has had an average volume of registrations of approximately 5 million families, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Number of Families in CadÚnico .

Source: Prepared by the Authors

In particular, the group of low-income families within CadÚnico includes those earning up to half a minimum wage per person, or those earning up to three minimum wages of total monthly income. The data available in the database make it possible, through a stratification or choice of profiles, to identify and characterize sets of families, individuals or even households with similar characteristics (MDS, 2020).

According to Barros; Carvalho and Mendonça (2010), CadÚnico has an almost census coverage of its target audience, given the diversity of data it stores, making it an important tool for analyzing and diagnosing the living conditions of its members, as well as for planning and conformation of social programs aimed at this population .

CadÚnico is used to choose different programs, projects, services and social benefits from the Federal Government. There are 27 (twenty-seven) user programs that use the register to select their beneficiaries, among them: the Bolsa Família Program; My home, my life; Green Bag; Child Labor Eradication Program; Elderly Card; Social Electricity Tariff ; Exemption from fees for public tenders; Social Phone and others. In this way, CadÚnico is still used by Brazilian states and municipalities as a basis for their subsidiary social projects and programs.

3. Performance Assessment of Social Programs

Social programs include individuals or groups that fit within the socioeconomic profile targeted by a given government policy, usually serving the poorest or the most socially vulnerable, providing means to improve their living conditions , food , health , education tion , housing , social inclusion and work, taking as a reference the social vulnerability of families

with average *per capita income* , beneficiaries or not of social programs, their compositions in the year 2018 can be observed, represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Histogram of Average Income *per capita* of Families Based on Income (CadÚnico) in 2018.

Source: Prepared by the Authors

On the right side of Figure 2, there are overlapping bars providing a comparison between the number of families assisted (in green) or not (in red) by the Bolsa Família Program in that year. On the right side are the families that did not receive the benefit (with the frequency on the y axis on a logarithmic scale) distributed in the range from 0 (zero) to 3 (three s) minimum wages, which, at time was BRL 954 (nine hundred and fifty-four reais) (AUDTEC GESTÃO CONTÁBIL, 2020). Otherwise, Bolsa Família beneficiary families are distributed with *per capita income* between R\$0 (zero) and R\$477.00 (four hundred and seventy-seven reais).

Inequality in income distribution has always represented an obstacle to development in Brazil, even though government action and investments represented by social programs were present. Therefore, it is necessary to understand and monitor its results through the evaluation of existing programs. Costa and Castanhar (1998) suggest that evaluation processes of social programs become a more common tool among managers, making it possible to better apply available resources and, consequently, obtain more qualified information for decisions based on the results obtained. It is observed that the effectiveness of social programs is related to measuring their performance and satisfying the expectations and needs of the individuals who participate in them (SARAIVA and NUNES, 2011, ROCHA *et al.* , 2014).

Serapioni (2016) teaches that the evaluation of social programs and policies follows a consensus on these elements that underlie the evaluation process :

- a) evaluation helps to develop insight into the value or merit of an intervention that aims to change the social reality of communities . It is observed, however, that this requires maturation time, suggesting continuous maintenance and improvement of the instrument over the years;
- b) Emphasis is placed on the systematicity and rigor of the data collection procedures that support the judgment of the merits and value of actions. However, it should be noted that such issues raised by Serapioni (2016) generally require the choice of techniques and, in parallel, interpretive and classification practices ;
- c) Evaluation is highlighted as an indispensable tool for decision-making , as it provides managers with information to improve the process of planning and managing programs, services and policies.

The results of an evaluation process highlight adjustments and improvements of social programs, as they take into account the needs of citizens (primary parameter in question), indicating whether the intended results are being obtained (SARAIVA and NUNES, 2011).

In this sense, the areas of action of social policies in Brazil are usually defined as: social security; health; education; job; sanitation; housing; land structure etc and, therefore, with a greater amplitude within the social fabric than public policies. According to the CGU Public Policy Assessment Guide (2019), this can be done through systematic review, meta-assessment or meta-analysis, including the survey and examination of qualitative, quantitative, or both research. According to Kravchuck and Schack (1996), a system that intends to evaluate performance must be a reflection of what managers, with decision-making power, expect to see and how they expect to respond. Therefore, when designing an evaluation system, it is initially important to define what to measure.

Abramovay *et al* . (2002) highlight the work of Caroline Moser and her group at the World Bank who, through an analytical approach to social vulnerability, systematized what they call the *Asset Vulnerability Framework* . This *framework* links income-poverty measures to the more dynamic dimensions of vulnerability related to the assets that poor families accumulate or lose in periods of economic crisis .

Traditional approaches to evaluating social programs suggest concepts related to the elaboration of planning stages, evidencing principles that structure and define the breadth of a social program. The Classical Test Theory (TCT) is one of these widely disseminated approaches with the aim of developing measurement instruments applicable in various situations (FAGUNDES and MOURA, 2009, ANDREOLI and SOUZA-FORMIGONI, 2013 ; SILVA, 2018).

Item Response Theory (IRT) has been increasingly used to assess instruments in different areas, such as education and health . Furthermore , by evaluating theoretical concepts that cannot be measured directly, it provides the equivalence of items representing different sociodemographic characteristics, eliminates redundant items and provides the opportunity for computerized adaptive tests. Nevertheless , it is able to determine a latent trait of the population to be analyzed (COOK *et al .* , 2008, JIANG and HESSER, 2009, KOPEC *et al .* , 2008, REISE and WALLER, 2009).

4. Methodological Procedures (the TRI)

Item Response Theory is a type of assessment based on statistical methods and mathematical models, where the calculation of the latent trait estimate and an associated error takes into account responses given by individuals and other properties of the items that are part of the item itself. assessment undertaken. That is, it is a statistical modeling developed to measure attributes that cannot be measured directly and an error associated with this measure. Thus, based on the observation of other variables related to this measure (secondary variables), it is possible to obtain an estimate of the behavior of a latent variable of interest (ALEXANDRE *et al .* , 2002, REISE; AINSWORTH and HAVILAND, 2005, VIEIRA *et al . al .* , 2011 and SILVA, 2018).

The IRT stands out for representing the probability of obtaining an expected response as a function of the ability of an individual or entity submitted to an evaluative item. The different representations of the relationship between the probability that the individual will respond to an evaluative item in the expected way as a function of the individual's latent trait and the characteristics of the items occur because, the greater the respondent's ability, the greater the probability of responding in the expected way. .

The IRT presents a series of statistical models of latent variables that must be selected according to the type of mathematical function adopted , the type of item under analysis, the parameters of the items to be investigated and the type of response process. The fundamental difference between these models consists of the probability ratio of an individual's expected response to the item in relation to the characteristics of that item. These items are characterized as polytomous or dichotomous (ANDRADE , TAVARES and VALLE, 2000).

When analyzing the CadÚnico databases, it is possible to observe the existence of items identified as dichotomous and polytomous. Taking as a reference the cumulative models:

Logistic Model of 2 (two) parameters (ML2P) and the Gradual Scale Model of Samejima (SAMEJIMA, 1969; VAN DER LINDEN and HAMBLETON, 1997).

From a set of 32 (thirty-two) variables that make up the FAMÍLIAS database of CadÚnico, at first, the choice of variables was based on items compatible with the Gradual Scale Model of the TRI (Item Response Theory).). Such Model suggests the concomitant use of categorical items with 2 (two) or more levels. It should be clarified that these 32 (thirty-two) variables were first categorized into 4 (four) distinct groups. However, one of these four groups, composed of 13 (thirteen) variables, was the one that best characterized the socioeconomic profiles of the FAMILIES database, the variables being : <cod_especie_domic_fam> (species of domicile); <cod_material_piso_fam> (Material predominant on the floor of the household); <cod_material_domic_fam> (Material predominant in the external walls of the domicile); <cod_agua_canalizada_fam> (If the household has running water); <cod_abaste_agua_domic_fam> (Water supply method); <cod_banheiro_domic_fam> (Existence of bathroom); <cod_escoa_sanitario_domic_fam> (Form of sanitary drainage); <cod_destino_garbage_domic_fam> (Garbage collection method); <cod_illuminacao_domic_fam> (Type of lighting); <cod_calcamanto_domic_fam> (Shoes); < cod_familia_indigena_fam> (Indigenous family) ; <ind_family_quilombola_fam> (Quilombola family); <marc_pbf> (Check if the family is a beneficiary of the Bolsa Família Program).

In the TRI, the calibration of the parameters of the selected items can be done, theoretically, using the entire base of registered families. According to Edelen and Reeve (2007) there are no definitive answers in relation to the size of the sample, but only general guidelines, such as: the need to increase the sample number must be proportional to the increase in the complexity of the model used; Obtaining smaller standard errors requires a larger sample number, although small samples may be adequate to evaluate the properties of a set of items.

For the purpose of this study, a stratified sampling proportional to the population of each unit of the federation (UF) was carried out to ensure the representativeness of each UF in the calibration of the parameters of the 13 (thirteen) items selected from the FAMÍLIAS do CadÚnico database (JELIHOVSCHI, 2014).

5. Discussion and Analysis of Results

In this study, 500,000 (five hundred thousand) families were selected from the CadÚnico database, distributed proportionally to the number of families in each state of the

federation. That is, a sufficient quantity to have enough respondents in each stratum of states and in the respective categories of responses. Analyzing Table 1, it is noted that an average of 10% of the families from each year of the CadÚnico Families base were used to calibrate the parameters .

Table 1 – Number of families registered each year in CadÚnico .

Year	Total Families	sample for calibration	% of Total
2012	4,582,169	500,000	10.91%
2013	4,936,690	500,000	10.13%
2014	5,395,665	500,000	9.27%
2015	5,122,861	500,000	9.76%
2016	4,880,295	500,000	10.25%
2017	5,130,647	500,000	9.75%
2018	4,807,996	500,000	10.40%

Source: Prepared by the Authors

In Table 2 are the numbers of families from each unit of the federation selected at random .

Table 2 – Number of families selected for calibration of item parameters.

cd_uf	wo w	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
11	RO	4,371	4,548	4,596	4,416	4,510	4,201	4,140
12	B.C	2,090	2,198	2,312	2,295	2,413	2,325	2,295
13	AM	9,059	10,453	10,664	10,757	11,533	11,243	11,625
14	RR	1,000	1,411	1,557	1,748	1,842	1,697	1,829

cd_uf	wo w	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
15	SH OV EL	23,640	24,784	25,156	25,924	27,720	27,646	28,854
16	AP	1,573	1,523	1,770	1,769	1,955	2,030	2,319
17	TO	4,793	4,371	4,961	5,163	5,365	5,188	5,181
21	BA D	27,221	27,621	27,117	26,826	28,626	27,440	27,100
22	IP	13,786	12,987	13,112	13,006	13,227	12,429	12,288
23	EC	35,567	34,591	33,217	33,470	34,872	33,673	33,627
24	RN	12,357	11,828	11,938	11,584	11,757	11,146	11,180
25	PB	15,668	14,935	15,111	14,824	15,333	14,742	14,541
26	FO OT	37,260	36,668	35,483	34,313	35,550	34,781	35,980
27	AL	12,892	12,606	12,305	12,235	12,589	12,071	11,996
28	IF	8,097	8,154	8,100	8,206	8,666	8,353	8,556
29	BA	58,448	57,768	56,547	56,014	58,019	56,414	55,521
31	MG	50,110	48,629	48,612	47,041	47,078	45,654	44,339
32	ES	8,383	8,398	8,355	8,327	8,376	7,678	7,656
33	RJ	29,878	30,493	30,794	30,265	30,814	30,293	31,820
35	SP	60,678	63,098	62,248	65,641	53,790	70,393	72,161
41	PR	22,417	21,673	21,640	22,047	22,598	21,693	20,862
42	SC	7,937	7,627	8,365	8,025	7,976	7,092	6,567
43	LO L	19,607	19,824	20,561	19,856	19,419	17,730	16,718

cd_uf	wo w	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
50	MS	6,184	6,824	7,237	7,694	7,900	7,271	7,054
51	MT	7,661	7,840	8,537	8,973	9,070	8,622	8,564
52	GO	14,217	14,214	14,934	15,179	15,282	14,858	14,259
53	DF	5,102	4,934	4,772	4,403	3,719	3,335	2,968
Total		499,996	500,000	500,001	500,001	499,999	499,998	500,000

Source: Prepared by the Authors

Next, a representation of the selection and adaptation format of the items taken from the CadÚnico Family database .

5.1. Selection and adaptation of CadÚnico items

To apply the models proposed in CadÚnico, the following recommendations made by Andrade, Tavares and Valle (2000) were taken into account:

- assessment of the nature of the items: the existence of dichotomous items (yes/no, true/false, right/wrong, for example), and/or polytomous (slightly dissatisfied, satisfied or very satisfied, for example) ;
- Assessment of the number of populations involved: a single one or more than one;
- Evaluation of the amount of latent traits that will be measured (dimensionality): one (one-dimensional model) or more than one (multidimensional model).

As for the first element (i), the selected items are dichotomous and polytomous, according to the classification presented in Table 3. As for the second element (ii), the population involved, it is the register of CadÚnico families over 7 years. (seven) years: 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018; therefore, there is more than one population. As for the third element (iii), dimensionality, it is dependent on the homogeneity of the set of items, and in this case, measuring a single latent trait , the **socioeconomic vulnerability of families**.

Socioeconomic vulnerability is dependent on a number of distinct elements; however, to satisfy the postulate of one-dimensionality, it is sufficient that there is a latent dominant trait. Thus, in a one-dimensional model, it is this dominant latent trait that is being measured by the items represented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Characteristics of selected items from CadÚnico.

Number	Code	Description	Type
8	cod_especie_domic_fam	Type of household	polytomic
11	cod_material_piso_fam	Predominant material on the floor of the home	polytomic
12	cod_material_domic_fam	Predominant material on the external walls of the home	polytomic
13	cod_agua_canalizada_fam	If the household has running water	dichotomous
14	cod_abaste_agua_domic_fam	Water supply form	polytomic
15	cod_banheiro_domic_fam	existence of bathroom	dichotomous
16	cod_escoa_sanitario_domic_fam	Sanitary drainage form	polytomic
17	cod_destino_lixo_domic_fam	Garbage collection method	polytomic
18	cod_iluminacao_domic_fam	lighting type	polytomic
19	cod_calçamento_domic_fam	pavement	polytomic
20	cod_familia_indigena_fam	indigenous family	dichotomous
21	ind_familia_quilombola_fam	quilombola family	dichotomous
32	marc_pbf	Check if the family is a beneficiary of the Bolsa Família Program	dichotomous

Source: Prepared by the Authors

Another essential assumption in the estimation process of the model parameters is the local independence (or conditional independence). It is assumed that for a given skill the answers to the different items of the questionnaire are independent. This independence is a consequence of the correct determination of the dimensionality of the data. Hambleton, Swaminathan and Rogers (1985) teach that one-dimensionality implies local independence, and

therefore requires only one and not two assumptions to be verified. Thus, items must be designed to satisfy the assumption of unidimensionality (a single latent trait being evaluated).

Furthermore, with the selected items in hand, to calibrate the parameters of the items, it was necessary to assess whether the options for each item were in accordance with the assumptions of the IRT.

5.2 Estimation of socioeconomic vulnerability levels

Having the items with their calibrated parameters (μ and β), it is possible to estimate a score for each family profile that corresponds to the latent measure (socioeconomic vulnerability level) for each response pattern to the CadÚnico items. Thus, each family was assigned its respective level of socioeconomic vulnerability .

Table 3 provides descriptive statistics on the level of socioeconomic vulnerability in each year.

Table 3 – Descriptive Statistics of the Socioeconomic Vulnerability Level .

Year	No	Minimum	1st Quartile	median	Average	3rd Quartile	Maximum
2012	4,582,169	-3.25619	-0.68501	-0.04015	-0.12740	0.55367	1.26767
2013	4,936,690	-3.25342	-0.62826	0.00033	-0.08309	0.55551	1.26767
2014	5,395,665	-3.25342	-0.58687	0.03264	-0.02159	0.55551	1.26767
2015	5,122,861	-3.25342	-0.51898	0.06224	0.02221	0.69912	1.27000
2016	4,880,295	-3.25342	-0.52104	0.06224	0.02201	0.69912	1.26767
2017	5,130,647	-3.25432	-0.48034	0.14714	0.07568	0.75057	1.26767
2018	4,807,996	-3.25340	-0.41050	0.16240	0.11010	0.75060	1.26770

Source: Prepared by the Authors

It is worth remembering that, with the equalization procedure, all the values presented are on the same scale, the scale created with the TRI, having the year 2012 as a reference.

The scores of the families present a certain range of variation, although it is reasonable to assume what the maximum and minimum limits would be, being those theoretically established. Thus, a family at the bottom of the score hierarchy is expected to answer “ no ” , or a lower rating category within the items. On the other hand, families with the best situations

within CadÚnico, theoretically, would answer “ yes ”, or even the highest category within the evaluated items (ALVES; SOARES and XAVIER, 2014).

Theoretical profiles are, therefore, simulated extreme cases with “answers” for all CadÚnico items in the least favorable and in the most favorable situations corresponding to the base and the top of the socioeconomic vulnerability level. Only one occurrence for each extreme case was added to the original 2018 database when estimating the levels of socioeconomic vulnerability of families (θ).

In the comparison of the estimated scores before and after the inclusion of the simulated profiles, the values shown in Table 4 were obtained. It is observed that the result did not change the values for the real cases: the mean and the difference between the 3rd and 1st quartile (equivalent to the standard deviation) were maintained. Therefore, it can be seen that it was possible to increase the amplitude of the scale with the inclusion of these simulated profiles.

Table 4 – Descriptive statistics of the value of θ by profile of families.

Estimate of θ	No	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Difference between 3rd and 1st quartile
Original profile	4807996	-3.2534	1.2677	0.111	1.1611
With simulated profiles	4807998	-3.6655	1.2687	0.111	1.1588

Source: Prepared by the Authors

This procedure can be replicated for the other years and the same maximum and minimum parameters will be obtained, because, with the equalization procedure, the parameters of the items of each year will be on the same scale and, therefore, the same maximum and minimum values will be obtained. on the scale.

It is worth mentioning that with the scale created by the TRI it was possible to “ rank ” the families and place them on the same scale. To estimate the theta values (θ) for each participating family, the method of the maximum marginal likelihood of complete information was used, using multiple groups using the “ *mirt* ” package of the computational environment R for the calculations (CHALMERS, 2012).

With the *ranking in hand* , the families evaluated with the lowest observed scores can be taken. It appears that families with lower scores were not identified taking into account a single sampling plan, but their segmentations were given as a function of the latent trait defined

a priori , that is, their socioeconomic vulnerabilities, defined based on the variables or evaluative items from the Cad Ú nico itself.

Through the scores of socioeconomic vulnerability calculated by the model, “ranges” are determined based on the scores of the Families base. Table 5 shows the family count by standard deviation range.

Table 5 – Number of families by θ (theta) value range .

Years	[0;-1.0[	[-1.0;-2.0[	[-2.0;-2.5[	[-2.5;-3.0[	[-3.0; -∞[
2012	1,590,649	704,986	57,180	5,793	120
2013	1,670,292	710,551	54,544	5,388	174
2014	1,785,014	695,121	50,313	4,549	189
2015	1,646,009	622,746	43,554	3,846	178
2016	1,576,012	595,573	40,778	3,443	193
2017	1,585,470	581,698	38,552	3,184	180
2018	1,448,894	516,898	32,960	2,649	141
totals	16,077,853	4,775,513	317,881	317,881	1,175

Source: Prepared by the Authors

At the same time, Figure 3 shows the numbers of families by score range over the years. It is worth emphasizing that, with the exception of families in the interval [3.0; -∞[, in the other intervals the number of families has been decreasing year by year.

Figure 3 – Number of families by score range between 2012 and 2018.

Source: Prepared by the Authors

Figures 4 and 5 show the histograms with the distribution of the calculated scores of the families over the years from 2012 to 2018. In the histogram bars, a grouping was performed by regions of origin of these families (North “ Green ” , Northeast “ Ocre ” , Southeast “ Blue ” , South “ Pink ” and Midwest “Red”).

Figure 4 – Histogram with the scores of the families in the years 2012 to 2017.

Source: Prepared by the Authors

Figure 5 – Histogram with the scores of the families in the year 2018.

Source: Prepared by the Authors

In the histograms of Figures 4 and 5, an asymmetry is observed in the distribution of the values of the Socioeconomic Vulnerability levels over the years. The scale created with the TRI allows for a good assessment of families with a level of vulnerability (θ) in the range $[-2.0; 0.5]$. However, it is evident that, as a function of the observed peaks, from then onwards $\theta = 0.5$ there are many families with scores above 0.5, although not as well distributed along the scale as those situated below this value.

Among the 13 (thirteen) items evaluated, with a total of 21 (twenty-one) difficulty parameters (b_i) between dichotomous and polytomous items, according to the description of the items presented in Table 1, 18 (eighteen) are situated in the region below the average ($\theta < 0$) and only 3 (three) with a value a little above the average, being: $\langle \text{cod_escoa_sanitario_domic_fam} \rangle$ ($b_7 = 0,088$); $\langle \text{cod_material_piso_fam} \rangle$ ($b_8 = 0,323$) and $\langle \text{marc_pbf} \rangle$ ($b = 0,472$), as seen in Table 6.

Table 6 – Difficulty parameters (b) in ascending order.

Item Code	difficulty parameter	Value
cod_specie_domic_fam	B	-17.019
cod_iluminacao_domic_fam	b1	-5.019
ind_familia_quilombola_fam	B	-4,567
cod_familia_indigena_fam	B	-4.111
cod_iluminacao_domic_fam	b2	-3,489
cod_material_domic_fam	b1	-2,915
cod_iluminacao_domic_fam	b3	-2,611
cod_material_piso_fam	b1	-2,294
cod_destino_lixo_domic_fam	b1	-2,077
cod_abaste_agua_domic_fam	B	-2,067
cod_material_piso_fam	b2	-1,781
cod_material_domic_fam	b2	-1,724
cod_banheiro_domic_fam	B	-1,688
cod_agua_canalizada_fam	B	-1,235
cod_destino_lixo_domic_fam	b2	-1.070
cod_material_domic_fam	b3	-0.863
cod_escoa_sanitario_domic_fam	b1	-0.451
cod_calçamento_domic_fam	B	-0.164
cod_escoa_sanitario_domic_fam	b2	0.088
cod_material_piso_fam	b3	0.323
marc_pbf	B	0.472

Source: Prepared by the Authors

It is important to note that there is a limitation in terms of the items available, which allow for the consistent assessment of only one region of the scale ($1.0 < \theta < = 4.0$). It is evident that the measure created by the TRI depends on better-prepared, pre-tested items, allowing the

assessment of a broader region of the created scale. Although certain intervals of the presented scale point to more vulnerable family groups, without the inclusion of new items there is no way to assess, with greater precision, other regions of the proposed socioeconomic vulnerability scale.

6. Conclusions and Final Considerations

Although the results show that families with scores above could $\theta > 0.5$ not be classified well, those with scores below the average, which in general are the focus of social inclusion policies, could be satisfactorily evaluated, according to the precepts of the IRT. In this way, the results obtained can be used as a sampling of families in a situation of socioeconomic vulnerability .

One of TRI's challenges is to produce a consistent assessment indicator , as CadÚnico was not designed for this purpose. However, its use made it possible to obtain complementary information in addition to income in the definition of socioeconomic vulnerability levels with the proposed assessment scale. Based on the scale created, greater detail is available in order to direct assistance to family groups and/or individuals as potential beneficiaries of social programs. By the way, there is a need to include other evaluative items, in order to debug the analysis initially proposed.

Although the measure of the latent trait (socioeconomic vulnerability) defined with the IRT proves to be consistent, it should not be taken as absolute if there is variation around the reference means. In the case of inclusion of new data (family records) or even evaluative items, the positions between families with very similar scores, their ordering may change. Therefore, together with the measure of the family score (θ) , it is necessary to associate the standard error (SE). The error measure conditions the means and their derived hierarchies to a variation; therefore, this measure is not absolute, but limiting in creating a *ranking* .

However, it is clear that the temporal evolution of the Brazilian regional socioeconomic vulnerability presents a very stable frequency , especially if we consider the range of analyzes of the last three years, that is, the years 2016, 2017 and 2018. In this sense, within the scores θ considered valid, the Northeast region has the highest participation of family groups in situations of vulnerability, followed shortly after by the Southeast and North regions of the country. On the other hand, the South region followed by the Center-West region presented, respectively, the lowest frequencies of vulnerable family groups.

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